
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK / ANALYTICAL NOTE

**Annulment of Passports of Political Prisoners
Removed from the Republic of Belarus
A Structural Element of the Mechanism of
Forced Expulsion through “Release”**

A Methodological Analytical Note for the
Identification and Interpretation of a Specific
Form of Repressive Practice

Document status:

Analytical Note

Document purpose:

Analytical documentation of the practice of passport annulment of expelled political prisoners and its interpretation within the framework of forced expulsion through “release”.

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Position within the Research Series

This document forms part of a research series dedicated to the study of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release.”

Documents in the Research Series

1. Analytical Report

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18444848

2. Concept Paper

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3. Methodological Glossary

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4. Definition Paper

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5. Methodological Framework

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18825890

6. Normative Legal Qualification

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7. Monitoring and Updating System

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18959571

8. Research Update

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19019474

9. Fourth Wave Legal Analysis

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The documents are interconnected and collectively form a unified conceptual and methodological framework.

Abstract

This analytical note documents the practice of passport invalidation affecting political prisoners of the Republic of Belarus who were removed from the country in 2025.

Based on information from independent media, human rights organisations, and direct testimonies, it is established that document invalidation is applied to deported individuals and currently covers at least 16 confirmed cases.

The analysis demonstrates that possession of a valid passport at the time of departure does not ensure its continued legal validity, as such documents are subsequently rendered invalid in official state databases of the Republic of Belarus.

This practice is interpreted within the framework of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”, whereby departure from the country does not result in the restoration of legal status, and state influence persists in other forms beyond national borders.

1. Introduction

In late March - early April 2026, media reports and human rights sources recorded cases in which the passports of former political prisoners of the Republic of Belarus, previously expelled beyond the country's borders, were recognized as invalid in the state databases of the Republic of Belarus.

These cases concern individuals who were released in 2025 and removed beyond the borders of Belarus as part of several waves of expulsion.

2. Sources and Verification of Information

The fact of passport annulment of expelled political prisoners is confirmed by a number of independent sources.

Current Time (Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty, RFE/RL) - an international media outlet, contains direct testimonies of former political prisoners, including references to at least 16 cases¹;

The Human Rights Center “Viasna” - a Belarusian human rights organization, records the existence of the problem and its connection to expelled political prisoners²;

Euroradio - an independent Belarusian media outlet, provides testimonies from members of one group whose passports were recognized as invalid³;

Zerkalo.io (“Zerkalo”) - an independent Belarusian online media outlet, confirms the existence of the problem and the absence of a clear explanation from state authorities⁴.

Additional information was obtained directly by the author of this document from expelled political prisoners, including their personal testimonies and visual confirmation of the status of their documents.

The convergence of data from independent sources, as well as the presence of direct testimonies from affected individuals, confirms this fact.

¹ Current Time (RFE/RL), 31 March 2026. <https://www.currenttime.tv/a/mozhno-skazat-chto-menya-lishili-grazhdanstva-vlasti-belarusi-annulirovali-pasporta-mnogih-politzaklyuchennyh-vyslannyh-iz-belarusi/33721233.html>

² Human Rights Center “Viasna”, April 2026. <https://spring96.org/ru/news/119932>

³ Euroradio, 3 April 2026. <https://euroradio.fm/ru/deportirovannyh-politzaklyuchennyh-v-belarusi-annuliruyut-pasporta>

⁴ Zerkalo.io (“Zerkalo”), 31 March 2026. <https://news.zerkalo.io/life/123928.html>

3. Confirmed Scope

At least 16 cases of passport annulment of expelled political prisoners have been confirmed. This figure is based on direct testimonies of affected individuals recorded in independent media. At the same time, testimonies from members of specific groups indicate that several individuals within these groups share the same document status; however, the publicly and documentarily confirmed minimum remains the number stated above.

4. Link to Waves of Expulsion

The recorded cases relate to individuals expelled as part of the following waves:

1st wave - 21 June 2025

2nd wave - 11 September 2025

3rd wave - 13 December 2025

Thus, the annulment of passports affects individuals expelled at different points in 2025.

5. Correlation Between Document Status at the Time of Expulsion and Thereafter

Within the practice of expulsion of political prisoners in 2025, cases have been recorded in which individuals were expelled beyond the borders of the Republic of Belarus both with valid passports and without documents.

The presence of a passport at the time of departure does not guarantee the preservation of its legal validity, as such passports are subsequently recognized as invalid in the state databases of the Republic of Belarus.

6. Mechanism of Document Annulment After Expulsion

The following sequence of actions has been established: a person is expelled beyond the borders of the country while formally holding a valid passport, after which this passport is recognized as invalid.

As a result, regardless of whether documents were present at the time of expulsion, the individual is left without a valid document.

7. Qualification within the Conceptual Framework

According to the concept of forced expulsion through “release”:

Forced expulsion through “release” constitutes a form of repressive practice in which release from places of deprivation of liberty is used by the state not as the completion of persecution and restoration of the individual’s legal status, but as an element of a mechanism for the person’s factual removal beyond the state’s jurisdiction without the adoption and formalization of a decision on expulsion.

The individual’s legal status thus remains incomplete, protection mechanisms do not ensure real safety, and refusal to leave the country leads to renewed isolation and exclusion from the legal and public sphere.

As a result, repressive impact does not cease but is transformed and ends only after the person has actually left the territory of the state, while its consequences persist beyond its borders.

New data show that expulsion as an act is completed at the moment of crossing the border; however, its consequences are not limited to this moment and are implemented through subsequent actions by the state affecting the individual’s status outside the country.

8. Key Finding

The annulment of passports of expelled political prisoners confirms that expulsion through “release” does not constitute the termination of repressive impact but represents its continuation in another form.

The existence of a valid passport at the time of departure does not imply the preservation of its legal validity, as the state retains control over the individual’s legal position and invalidates the document after expulsion.

Thus, the distinction between expulsion with documents and without documents is purely formal and does not affect the final status of the individual, which is characterized by the absence of a recognized and protected legal position.

9. Conclusion

The recorded practice of passport annulment confirms the implementation of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release”, in which the departure of the individual beyond the borders of the country is not accompanied by the restoration of their legal status and does not terminate the state’s impact.

The practice of passport annulment after expulsion further demonstrates that the state retains instruments of control and influence over the legal position of expelled individuals beyond its territory, continuing to affect their situation outside the country.

This confirms the systemic nature of the mechanism, in which the impact on the individual does not cease after departure but is carried out in other forms.

Annex

Visual confirmation of document invalidation in an official state database

The result of a validity check of a document belonging to one of the political prisoners removed from the Republic of Belarus confirming its status as invalid.

The text in the image is a direct and faithful translation from Russian into English.

To verify the validity of a document (passport, residence permit), enter the full document number (for example, MP1234567).

Document [MP XXXXXXXX] is invalid. The check was performed on 02.04.2026 at XX:XX:XX.

Certain elements, including time data, have been deliberately obscured to protect the identity of the individual concerned.
